

Preparation and Properties of a new Thiocyanatopentacyanorhenate (II) Anion.*

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A new anion thiocyanatopentacyanorhenate (II) has been prepared from aquopentacyanorhenate (II). K, Ag, and Cu salts have been prepared in pure form. The properties of this anion are compared with those of normal hexacyanorhenate (II).

The preparation and properties of aquopentacyanorhenates (II) and their close analogy with those of aquopentacyanoferrates (II) have been reported by Sen¹. Aquopentacyanorhenate (II) is found to be quite stable in aqueous medium and the H₂O molecule is strongly co-ordinated. However CN⁻ group can replace the H₂O molecule and form normal hexacyanorhenate (II)². CNS⁻ co-ordinates readily with metals forming a large variety of compounds. In this paper the existence of a new quite stable complex ion [Re(CN)₅(CNS)]⁴⁻ is reported. The chemical, magnetic and spectral properties of this ion as well as of [Re(CN)₆]⁴⁻ have been studied in some detail.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents and chemicals : KReO₄ used in this investigation was of 99.8% purity and procured from Messrs. Johnson Matthey and Co. Limited, England. All other chemicals used were either pro-analyst, E. Merck or B.D.H., A.R. quality.

Methods of analysis : Rhenium was estimated by internal electrolysis method³ after decomposing the compounds with peroxide fusion and separating rhenium by precipitating it as Re₂S₇ and dissolving the precipitate with Na₂O₂. Carbon was estimated by micro combustion and nitrogen by micro-Dumas method. K₂Cr₂O₇ was used for these micro determinations to fix the rhenium as KReO₄. However it was observed that the carbon estimation was always low in the case of alkali metal salt which was due to the formation of alkali metal carbonate. Alkali metals were estimated as sulphate after decomposing the compound with concentrated H₂SO₄. Cu was estimated by standard method after preliminary decomposition by fuming with H₂SO₄. For the estimation of Ag, the compound was just moistened with one or two drops of conc. H₂SO₄ in a Pt-basin and heated on a low flame. When the evolution of white fumes ceased, the basin was cooled and a few drops of conc. HNO₃ was added to this. The basin was again gently heated to dryness and the mass was taken out with dilute nitric acid and the silver was precipitated by adding HCl as usual. It was observed that under the above experimental condition such low concentration of

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1. S. Sen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1962, **315**, 315.
2. S. Sen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1965, **340**, 82.
3. Sabyasachi Sarkar, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1969 **46**, 684.

SO_4^{2-} does not interfere in the estimation of chloride. Sulphur was estimated as BaSO_4 after oxidising the complex with Br_2 water by prolonged keeping on a boiling waterbath.

Preparation of $\text{K}_3[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$: The principal method is a two step synthesis involving first the preparation of sodium salt and then conversion of this salt to the desired compound *via* ion exchanger as reported by Sen⁴. It is observed by the present author that with slight alteration of Sen's procedures the time for the conversion of KReO_4 to NaReO_4 is saved. Thus a mixture of KReO_4 and NaCN was reduced by 2.5% Na/Hg . The mixed alkali metal salt of aquopentacyanorhenate (II) was converted into free acid with the help of cation exchange resin (Dowex 50W-X8-H form) and the free acid was just neutralised with KHCO_3 and concentrated in vacuum. The product was purified with alcohol as in Sen's method. The yield was 75% based on the rhenium used. The anhydrous material obtained from vacuum P_2O_5 drying (after constant weight) gave the following analysis (Found: K, 27.2, 26.97; Re, 42.8, 43.1; N, 16.3, 16.34; calculated for $\text{K}_3[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5]$: K, 27.0; Re, 42.9; N, 16.16%).

Preparation of $\text{K}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$: A concentrated solution of K-salt of aquopentacyanorhenate (II) was refluxed with excess of KCNS for 45–60 min. The deep brown colour on boiling faded to clear orange red. This was allowed to cool and filtered. The complex salt was tried to crystallise in vacuum desiccator but it is found that in aqueous medium reverse reaction with the formation of aquopentacyanorhenate (II) occurred. So after boiling for about 1 hr. when the solution has acquired a clear orange red colour it was cooled, filtered and then treated with acetone, when a yellow solid separated. The acetone solution was decanted off. The yellow solid was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and again reprecipitated with acetone. This process was repeated several times till the washed acetone was free from KCNS (tested with Fe^{3+}). The salt was dried in vacuum over H_2SO_4 . Yield was quantitative. (Found: K, 29.2, 29.1; Re, 34.8, 34.83; N, 15.7, 15.84; S, 5.8, 5.7; C, 12.5, 12.3; calculated for $\text{K}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$: K, 29.12, Re, 34.69; N, 15.64; S, 5.77; C, 13.41%).

Preparation of $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$: On addition of filtered, dilute solution of silver nitrate to an aqueous solution of potassium thiocyanatopentacyanorhenate (II), heavy brownish yellow precipitate of the silver salt was formed. It was filtered and washed with water and finally with alcohol and dried in vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 in the dark. A typical preparation gave the following analysis (Found: Ag, 53.50; Re, 23.3; N, 10.57; S, 3.92; calculated for $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$: Ag, 53.46; Re, 23.12; N, 10.42; S, 3.85%).

Preparation of $\text{Cu}_2[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})], 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: A strong solution of copper sulphate was added to a solution of potassium thiocyanatopentacyanorhenate (II). The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered and washed thoroughly with water till free from sulphate. The brownish red precipitate was dried in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 . (Found: Cu, 20.91; Re, 30.75; N, 13.65; S, 4.92; calculated for $\text{Cu}_2[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})], 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Cu, 20.85; Re, 30.57; N, 13.78; S, 5.09%).

4. S. Sen, Doctoral thesis, 1960, Calcutta University.

Chemical properties of $[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]^{4-}$ and its salts : The ion in aqueous solution gives precipitates with the following other cations : Fe^{2+} (bluish white), Ni^{2+} (bluish green), Co^{2+} (bright green), Mn^{2+} (white) and Fe^{3+} gives no precipitate but a deep blue solution. The constitution of these precipitates has not been investigated. The potassium salt is slightly hygroscopic in nature but other insoluble salts are not hygroscopic. In aqueous solution, the thiocyanatopentacyanorhenate (II) ion has a tendency to hydrolyse to more stable aquopentacyanorhenate (II) ion. This was observed by a colour change of dilute aqueous solution of $K_4[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]$, from pale yellow to violet brown. This hydrolysis process might be written as : $[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]^{4-} + H_2O \rightleftharpoons [Re(CN)_5(H_2O)]^{3-} + CNS^-$. The rate of hydrolysis was quite slow in neutral medium and at room temperature. It was hastened when the solution was made acidic and temperature was raised. Study on the hydrolysis of $[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]^{4-}$ ion is in progress. In the presence of oxidising agent like Br_2 the pale yellow solution of $[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]^{4-}$ was changed to deep green colour; on standing, this colour was changed to brown violet indicating the formation of aquopentacyanorhenate (II). The deep green solution shows the presence of SO_4^{2-} with the help of characteristic $BaSO_4$ test indicating the decomposition of the thiocyanatopentacyanorhenate (II) immediately with the formation of aquopentacyanorhenate (III) and oxidation of CNS^- . The oxidation reaction is presumed to proceed in the following manner :

Similar observation was noticed by Sen⁴ in the case of hexacyanorhenate (II). Attempts were also made to prepare the acid $H_4[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]$. By passing an aqueous solution of $K_4[Re(CN)_5(CNS)]$ through cation exchange resin, Dowex 50W-X8-H form, the violet acid $H_3[Re(CN)_5(H_2O)]$ was formed instead.

Preparation of $K_4[Re(CN)_6]$: It was prepared in the same way as described by Sen². A typical analysis is given below : (Found : K, 31.15; Re, 37.5; N, 16.9; calculated for $K_4[Re(CN)_6]$: K, 31.21; Re, 37.35; N, 16.86%).

Magnetic susceptibilities : All measurements were made with a Gouy balance using $CuSO_4$ pentahydrate as calibrant. A field strength of 8500 Gauss was taken. χ^{Mol} values were obtained by usual diamagnetic correction applying Pascal's constant. Each moment was calculated as $\mu = 2.84 \sqrt{(\chi_{Cor}^{Mol} \cdot T)}$. The potassium salts used in this measurement are slightly hygroscopic in nature, hence the Gouy tube when packed with substance is weighed after attaining constant weight in vacuum desiccator. Moments of other salts as well as moments at different temperatures of the corresponding anions have not been investigated.

Infra red spectra : All spectra were recorded using a Beckman IR-8 spectrophotometer. The spectra were taken on Nujol mulls or pressed KBr disks in the rock salt region.

Ultraviolet and visible absorption spectra : These were measured on aqueous solutions of alkali salts using a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer.

DISCUSSION

General: In the sequence $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^{3-}$, $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CO})]^{3-}$, $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{NO})]^{2-}$, $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$, the first one is extremely stable, the second and third are quite stabler than the last, symmetrically co-ordinated anion $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$.

It is well known⁵ that a lower symmetry crystalline field (e.g., a slight distortion from a regular octahedron) can introduce intensity into a transition which otherwise cannot be observed. In this sequence preparation of another less symmetric anion $[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]^{4-}$ has been undertaken.

Magnetic properties: It would certainly be reasonable to expect maximum spin pairing with the ligands like CN^- , CNS^- . Thus here the electronic configuration of the rhenium ion would be T_{2g}^5 and there would be one unpaired electron. The magnetic moment for this anion should be 1.73 B.M. according to spinonly formula. Actually the recorded values are 0.55 B.M. and 0.62 B.M. for $\text{K}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$ and $\text{K}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$ respectively at 301°K. These low values may be due to very large values of the spin-orbit coupling constant in case of the heavy elements of the third transition series. For this series KT/A value is of the order of 0.02 to 0.1 and hence low magnetic moments are expected even at ordinary temperature as explained by Kotani⁶.

Infrared spectra: CN^- and CNS^- absorb in the range 2170–2040 cm^{-1} and 2150–2080, 810–690 cm^{-1} respectively⁷. $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$: The silver salt was used here as it is not hygroscopic. $\nu(\text{C} \equiv \text{N})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ are observed at 2085, 2100 and 717 cm^{-1} respectively. The C—S stretching frequency is much shorter than 820 cm^{-1} indicating the linkage: M—S—C \equiv N as calculated by Lewis, Nyholm and Smith⁸. $\text{Ag}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$: The infrared spectrum of this anion has not been previously reported. Two sharp stretchings at 2030 and 2082 cm^{-1} are believed to be due to $\nu(\text{C} \equiv \text{N})$.

Visible and ultraviolet spectra: Identical electronic spectra are obtained for the two anions. They show one spin allowed transition and two charge transfer bands are evidenced by their ϵ values. The results are tabulated below:

TABLE I

Salt	Band position ($m\mu$)	cm^{-1}	ϵ
$\text{K}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_6]$	221	45250	15800
	252	39680	18100
	420	23810	12.1
$\text{K}_4[\text{Re}(\text{CN})_5(\text{CNS})]$	221	45250	14800
	252	39680	16100
	420	23810	18.7

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